

Supplementary Table 1. Laboratory findings of COVID-19 patients.					
Laboratory markers	Reference range	Survivors (n=76)	Non-survivors (n=35)	p value	Statistical test
WBC, x10 ⁹ /l	4.0-10.0	6.725 (5.345; 9.84)	8.98 (5.36; 11.84)	0.129	U Mann Whitney test
Lymphocyte count, x10⁹/L	1.5-3.5	1.145 (0.69; 1.57)	0.76 (0.48; 1.33)	0.031	
Monocyte count, x10⁹/L	0.2-0.8	0.6 (0.45; 0.835)	0.39 (0.28; 0.75)	0.021	
Neutrophil count, x10 ⁹ /l	2.05-20.05	5.005 (3.295; 7.435)	6.655 (3.81; 10.39)	0.136	
Eosinophil count, x10 ⁹ /l	0.04-0.4	0.015 (0; 0.05)	0.01 (0; 0.06)	0.869	
Basophil count, x10 ⁹ /l	0.02-0.1	0.02 (0.01; 0.03)	0.02 (0.01; 0.03)	0.567	
RBC, x10 ¹² /l	4.2-5.7	4.33 (3.64; 4.82)	4.1 (3.41; 4.76)	0.207	
Haemoglobin, g/dL	13.5-16.5	12.38 (11.76 - 13.0)	11.89 (10.78 - 13.01)	0.414	T-test
Haematocrit, %	40-53	36.56 (34.82 - 38.29)	35.73 (32.67 - 38.79)	0.614	
MCV, fL	84-98	87.9 (84.4; 90.6)	89.5 (85.6; 93.5)	0.114	U Mann Whitney test
MCH, pg	27-31	29.8 (28.4; 31)	29.9 (27.8; 31.1)	0.875	
MCHC, g/dl	32-36	33.8 (33; 34.7)	33.3 (32.3; 34.2)	0.063	
RDW-SD, fL	36.3-47.3	43.7 (39.8; 50.4)	47.05 (43; 50)	0.021	
Platelet count, x10 ⁹ /l	130-400	223 (161.5; 312)	199 (143; 264)	0.127	
C-reactive protein, mg/L	< 5	45.7 (9.6; 88.8)	80.3 (40.5; 128)	0.003	
Procalcitonin, ng/mL	< 0.5	0.1695 (0.068; 0.347)	0.388 (0.199; 1.04)	<0.001	
Total bilirubin, mg/dL	0.3-1.2	0.6 (0.41; 0.96)	0.62 (0.4; 0.73)	0.844	
AST, U/L	< 50	44.6 (28.3; 69.4)	61.5 (34.7; 111)	0.109	
ALT, U/L	< 50	36.9 (23.9; 62.3)	29.7 (21.7; 56.8)	0.271	
ALP, U/L	40-129	68 (55; 102)	97 (78; 145)	0.027	
GGT, U/L	< 60	59.95 (19.9; 128)	75.3 (46.3; 293)	0.106	
LDH, U/L	< 250	291 (201; 381)	301 (270; 628)	0.082	
Lactate, mmol/L	1.1-2.4	2.32 (1.91; 3.02)	2.52 (1.88; 3.21)	0.375	
Amylase, U/L	28-100	67.5 (44.8; 76)	129.95 (62.9; 197)	0.49	

Lipase, U/L	13-60	44.1 (26.2; 75.9)	29 (15.5; 54.3)	0.107	U Mann Whitney test
Creatinine, mg/dL	0.67-1.17	0.985 (0.75; 1.21)	1.19 (0.85; 1.83)	0.012	
BUN, mg/dL	7.09.2020	15.84 (12.2; 24.67)	28.365 (17.41; 59.35)	0.012	
Glucose, mg/dL	70-99	124 (96.1; 147)	136 (102; 163)	0.553	
Fibrinogen, mg/dL	200-393	468 (340; 652)	403 (295; 585)	0.314	
aPTT, s	25.4-36.9	31.7 (29; 36)	35.4 (30.1; 40.4)	0.149	
PT-INR	0.8-1.2	1.16 (1.1; 1.32)	1.23 (1.11; 1.55)	0.166	
PT, s	9.4-12.5	13.2 (12.4; 15)	14.5 (12.6; 18)	0.107	
D-dimer, ng/mL	< 500	1410.5 (867; 2849)	2409 (1170; 11412)	0.026	
Sodium, mmol/L	136-145	136.5 (134; 139.5)	136.3 (134.1; 140.3)	0.585	
Potassium, mmol/L	3.5-5.1	4.1 (3.66; 4.58)	4.08 (3.76; 4.63)	0.646	
Magnesium, mg/dL	1.6-2.4	1.94 (1.73; 2.09)	1.69 (1.61; 1.92)	0.0374	
Calcium, mg/dL	8.8-10.2	8.66 (8.47 - 8.83)	8.32 (8.02 - 8.62)	0.04254	T-test
Troponin, ng/L	< 14.5	22.7 (10.2; 36.3)	43.25 (27.6; 78.6)	<0.001	U Mann Whitney test
Creatine kinase-MB, U/L	< 25	19.5 (16; 39)	26.5 (18; 37.5)	0.478	
CK, U/L	< 190	90 (44; 363)	136.5 (50; 303)	0.674	
NT-proBNP, pg/mL	< 125	792 (154; 1952)	3734.5 (740; 12080)	0.003	
Acidity-basicity	7.35-7.45	7.46 (7.38; 7.5)	7.415 (7.34; 7.5)	0.386	T-test
PaCO ₂ , mmHg	35-46	33.607 (26.97 - 40.24)	32.72 (28.6 - 36.83)	0.801	
PaO ₂ , mmHg	70-100	69.693 (59.3 - 80.09)	56.41 (45.96 - 66.85)	0.071	
HCO ₃ , mmol/L	21-26	23.06 (20.49 - 25.63)	20.01 (17.38 - 22.63)	0.096	U Mann Whitney test
Hemoglobin oxygen saturation,	> 96	94.2 (89.4; 95.7)	88.85 (77.8; 93.5)	0.039	
Base excess, mmol/L	(-2.0) - 3.0	2.6 (0.8; 3.1)	5 (2.45; 9.25)	0.022	
Oxyhemoglobin, %	> 96	93.6 (88.6; 95.4)	87.3 (77.35; 92.6)	0.022	
Deoxyhemoglobin, %	0-5	5.9 (4.3; 11.2)	11.1 (6.45; 22.05)	0.071	

Abbreviations: ALP, alkaline phosphatase; ALT, alanine aminotransferase; AST, aspartate

aPTT, activated partial thromboplastin time; BUN, blood urea nitrogen; CK, creatine kinase; GGT, γ -glutamyl transferase; LDH, lactate dehydrogenase; MCH, mean corpuscular hemoglobin; MCHC, mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration; MCV, mean corpuscular volume; NT-proBNP, N-terminal pro B-type natriuretic peptide; PT, prothrombin time; PT-INR, prothrombin international normalized ratio; RBC, red blood cell count; RDW-SD, red blood cell distribution width standard deviation; WBC white blood cell count.